

Identification of Core Anomalies via Neutron Noise under Multiplicative Detector Signal Distortion

Antonio Galia^{1*}, Paolo Vinai¹, Christophe Demazière¹

¹Department of Physics, Chalmers University of Technology, 41296 Gothenburg, Sweden

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803554

ABSTRACT

This work addresses the identification of anomalies in nuclear reactor cores through the solution of an inverse problem based on neutron noise. Two methodologies are investigated: Exhaustive Search (ES) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). The performance of both approaches is evaluated in the case of detector signals affected by a distortion. This distortion is modeled as a multiplicative component dependent on the signal itself. To reduce sensitivity to measurement quality, we introduce within the ES framework a Bayesian approach to produce solutions in terms of probability density function in the solution space. In addition, we develop a denoising technique that reconstructs physically consistent clean signals. Results show that ES achieves the highest accuracy and robustness when combined with signal reconstruction, and the ANN model trained on distorted data maintain stable performance across all distortion levels.

Keywords: Core monitoring, neutron noise, source inverse problem, noisy detector signals

1. INTRODUCTION

In a nuclear power plant, core monitoring and diagnostics based on neutron noise use the fluctuations of neutron flux measurements under normal operative conditions to detect anomalies. These fluctuations may raise concerns about nuclear safety, as the underlying cause of these anomalies could compromise fuel integrity and potentially lead to radioactive releases. The identification of an anomaly involves three key tasks: *i*) classification of the type of phenomenon; *ii*) localization of the issue in terms of position and spatial extent; and *iii*) characterization of the forcing oscillation, specifically its amplitude and phase. This information can be extracted from the neutron noise recorded by the available detector measurements by solving an inverse problem. This problem is nonlinear, non-convex, and high-dimensional, involving a large number of possible configurations within the solution search space. Therefore, traditional gradient-based and metaheuristic optimization algorithms may struggle to find the exact solution, either due to instability or to the rugged landscape of the loss function to be minimized. This motivates the investigation of more robust methodologies such as Exhaustive Search (ES) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). An ES approach consists of exploring all possible solution candidates and offers several advantages: *i*) it guarantees that the global minimum is found; *ii*) it is inherently stable, as it does not suffer from convergence issues; *iii*) it allows verification of the uniqueness of the solution; and *iv*) it can combine multiple candidate solutions to construct the final result. This approach may be computationally demanding due to the large number of candidate solutions; however, in [1] we show that an adjoint-based formalism enables fast computation of detector responses and consequently makes an Exhaustive Search in the solution space not only feasible but also computationally efficient. On the other hand, ANNs provide instantaneous execution and are well suited for handling large datasets. However, their physical interpretability is not always straightforward. A comparison between the two approaches therefore allows one to assess whether any inaccuracy in the inverse solution arises from limitations of the model itself or from the intrinsic complexity of the problem. One

*galiaa@chalmers.se

of the main challenges that increases this complexity stems from the ill-posed nature of inverse problems, which makes the inverse solution highly sensitive to the quality of the measurements used by the methodology. In this work, we investigate how these two approaches perform when detector signals are distorted by multiplicative noise. To avoid ambiguity, we use the term “distortion” to refer to signal noise, distinguishing it from neutron noise caused by the physical anomaly. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the formalization of the inverse problem; Section 3 describes the implementation of the two methodologies introduced above; Section 4 introduces a technique used in the framework of ES to reconstruct the clean signal when multiplicative distortion affects the detector measurements; and Sections 5 and 6 compare and discuss the results obtained with the two approaches.

2. PRELIMINARIES

2.1. The inverse problem

The fluctuations in neutron flux result from variations of the physical system and can therefore be attributed to perturbations in nuclear cross sections. In neutron noise theory [2], the problem of anomaly identification is formalized as a source inverse problem, where the cross-section perturbations are associated with an external noise source, while the signal provided by detectors is transformed into a physical quantity called neutron noise, representing the deviation from its mean value. Using a linear perturbative approach, the theory yields a linear transport equation in the complex frequency domain that describes the system’s response to a given noise source:

$$\mathcal{B}_0(\omega)\delta\psi(\omega) = -\delta\mathcal{B}(\omega)\psi_0, \quad -\infty < \omega < +\infty, \quad (1)$$

with appropriate boundary and initial conditions. In the last equation, ω denotes the frequency; \mathcal{B}_0 and ψ_0 are the Fourier-transformed linear transport operator and the steady-state transport solution under reference conditions, respectively; and $\delta\mathcal{B}$ and $\delta\psi$ represent the perturbed operator and the neutron noise. The right-hand side of Equation (1) constitutes the neutron noise source that is the unknown of the problem. In the work [1], we formalize the problem in the general case of N_s noise sources of arbitrary size and N_d detectors, using the duality principle. The adjoint noise functions $\delta\psi_d^\dagger$, associated with the detectors, are obtained by solving the linear adjoint noise equations:

$$\mathcal{B}_0^\dagger(\omega)\delta\psi_d^\dagger(\omega) = \delta S_d^\dagger(\omega), \quad d = 1, \dots, N_d. \quad (2)$$

The symbol “ \dagger ” denotes the adjoint, and δS_d^\dagger are the adjoint noise sources defined using the detector characteristics and Dirac-delta distributions in phase space and frequency domain. This approach allows to efficiently determine the detector responses, and the three inverse tasks can be compactly expressed as:

$$(\mathbf{Y}_v \circ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x})\mathbf{\Gamma}^* = \mathbf{d}. \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) is a complex-valued equation, where: the vector \mathbf{d} contains the N_d measurements of the neutron noise at the peak frequency observed by the detectors; $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ is a vector of size N_s , containing the periodic functions of the type $\gamma e^{i\omega\varphi}$, which characterize the perturbations, and the symbol $*$ denotes the complex conjugate; \mathbf{x} is localization variable, containing the coordinates of the six surfaces surrounding each of the N_s volumes hosting the noise sources; the selection operator \mathbf{C} is defined such that $\mathbf{C}_i(\mathbf{x}_s) = 1$ if $V_i \in V(\mathbf{x}_s)$, and zero otherwise, where V_i is the volume of an element in the core geometry and $V(\mathbf{x}_s)$ the volume hosting a noise source s ; and the symbol “ \circ ” denotes element-wise product along the corresponding directions. Furthermore, the tensor \mathbf{Y}_v depends on the perturbation classes v , and contains the partial inner products:

$$Y_{d,s,i} = \int_{V_i} d\mathbf{r} \int_0^\infty dE \int_{4\pi} \delta\psi_d^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{\Omega}, E, \omega) f_{v_s}^*(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{\Omega}, E, \omega) d\mathbf{\Omega}. \quad (4)$$

This expression arises from the relationship between direct and adjoint noise equations. Classical notation is used for the phase-space variables, and the function f_{v_s} to be inferred is the noise source shape function of the noise source s . It is defined over the entire phase space providing a physical model that is representative of the oscillatory phenomenon, e.g. the ε/d model for mechanical vibrations [3]. The tensor \mathbf{Y}_v has dimensions $N_d \times N_s \times N_i$ and can be precomputed for the N_d detectors, N_i volume elements, and N_v perturbation classes. The partial integration over the spatial domain is analogous to homogenizing the system into a coarse geometry, where the regions correspond to the elements in which the perturbations are to be localized. This procedure greatly reduces the size of the inverse problem, making it independent of the size of the direct and adjoint problems, which can still be modeled using a high-order transport operator on fine spatial and energy meshes. The classification and localization tasks involve non-linear relationships between neutron noise sources and detector measurements, whereas the characterization task can be addressed by inverting the linear system of equations obtained by fixing \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{x} . Solving the inverse problem consists of determining \mathbf{v} , \mathbf{x} and $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ such that discrepancies between measured and predicted values, i.e. between right- and left-hand sides of Equation (3), are minimized.

2.2. Detector signals and distortion

Real neutron noise measurements are typically available in the form of the Power Spectral Density (PSD) defined as:

$$\text{PSD}_{dd'}(\hat{\omega}) = \delta\phi(\mathbf{r}_d, \hat{\omega})\delta\phi^*(\mathbf{r}_{d'}, \hat{\omega}), \quad (5)$$

where $\delta\phi$ denotes the scalar neutron noise in the detector energy range, and $\hat{\omega}$ the peak frequency of the signal in the Fourier domain. The diagonal of the PSD matrix is called Auto Power Spectral Density (APSD) and contains the squared signal amplitudes, while the off-diagonal elements provide the Cross Power Spectral Density (CPSD) as well as the phase shifts between detectors. These data must be processed to construct the complex-valued right-hand side of Equation (3). The amplitude of the neutron noise in each detector can be directly computed as:

$$|\delta\phi_d| = \sqrt{\text{PSD}_{dd}}, \quad (6)$$

while the phases can be obtained by solving the following linear system of equations:

$$\varphi_d - \varphi_{d'} = \arg(\text{PSD}_{dd'}), \quad d = 1, \dots, N_d \quad d' = d + 1, \dots, N_d. \quad (7)$$

This system contains $\frac{N_d}{2}(N_d - 1)$ equations and N_d unknowns, and has rank $N_d - 1$. This rank deficiency implies that absolute phases cannot be determined, and only relative phase shifts between detectors are known. Therefore, we set an arbitrary offset by choosing $\varphi_1 = 0$ and solve for the least-squares solution. Finally, each element of the vector \mathbf{d} is computed as:

$$\mathbf{d}_d = |\delta\phi_d| e^{i\hat{\omega}\varphi_d}. \quad (8)$$

Because of the linear model for the neutron noise, the peak frequency is used in Equations (2) and (4) to determine the adjoint neutron noise $\delta\psi^\dagger$, the noise source shape functions f_v as well as the periodic function $\mathbf{\Gamma}$. To perform a sensitivity analysis of the methodologies with respect to the quality of measurements, we decided to alter the APSD of each detector independently, using a multiplicative distortion as follows:

$$\widetilde{\text{PSD}}_{dd} = (1 + \varepsilon_d)\text{PSD}_{dd}. \quad (9)$$

In this equation, the symbol $\widetilde{}$ denotes a distorted quantity, and $\varepsilon_d \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \varepsilon)$ is a distortion factor sampled from a Gaussian distribution centered at zero with standard deviation ε . For physical reasons, we accept sampled values such that $\varepsilon_d > -1$. We refer to the parameter ε , which characterizes the overall detector behavior, as the sensitivity parameter. The remaining elements of the $\widetilde{\text{PSD}}$ matrix can be computed accordingly.

3. METHODOLOGIES

3.1. Exhaustive Search

The ES approach evaluates the discrepancy functional for all possible noise source configurations in a search space \mathcal{S} . Each configuration is defined by the parameter vector $\mathbf{q} = [v, \mathbf{x}]$, from which we construct a map to the unit-source detector responses as follows:

$$\mathbf{q} \mapsto \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}) = (\mathbf{Y}_v \circ \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}). \quad (10)$$

The matrix \mathbf{A} has dimensions $N_d \times N_s$. If it is full column rank, $\mathbf{\Gamma}^*$ can be computed as the unique least-squares solution using its pseudoinverse:

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}^*(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{A}^+(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{d}. \quad (11)$$

This equation shows that the vector $\mathbf{\Gamma}^*$ depends indirectly on the configuration \mathbf{q} and is chosen as the solution for which the predicted detector responses ($\mathbf{A}\mathbf{\Gamma}^*$) are best explained by the linearity of the neutron noise equation. Specifically, the detector responses are expected to result from the superposition of effects due to multiple noise sources. The discrepancy functional F is based on the L2-norm and is defined as:

$$F(\mathbf{q}) = \|\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{\Gamma}^*(\mathbf{q})\|_2^2. \quad (12)$$

The ES algorithm performs three steps in Equations (10) to (12) for all values of \mathbf{q} , and selects the global minimum (GM) solution such that:

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{GM}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{q} \in \mathcal{S}} F(\mathbf{q}). \quad (13)$$

The discrepancy functional provides insights into the distribution of the candidate solutions within the solution space. If the global minimum is well isolated from other candidates, it can be unambiguously identified as the best solution. However, when signals are affected by distortion, it becomes more likely to observe a cluster of candidates with similar discrepancies, increasing the uncertainty in distinguishing between solutions. To address this issue, we adopt a Bayesian approach to reconstruct the probability density function underlying the solution and to quantify the spatial uncertainty associated with the noise source. The posterior $p(\mathbf{q}|\mathbf{d})$, representing the probability that a configuration \mathbf{q} explains the observed data \mathbf{d} , is directly proportional to the likelihood of observing \mathbf{d} given \mathbf{q} , multiplied by the prior knowledge about \mathbf{q} :

$$p(\mathbf{q}|\mathbf{d}) \propto p(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{q})p(\mathbf{q}). \quad (14)$$

The likelihood $p(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{q})$ can be expressed in terms of the discrepancy functional as follows:

$$p(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{q}) \propto e^{-\frac{F_{\text{GM}} - F(\mathbf{q})}{F_{\text{GM}}}}, \quad (15)$$

where F_{GM} denotes the minimum value of F . In this work, the prior $p(\mathbf{q})$ is assumed to be uniform and thus does not influence the shape of the posterior distribution. We normalize then the posterior to one, and we use it to construct a probability density function in space which depends on the position vector \mathbf{r} rather than the localization vector \mathbf{x} . For this purpose, we consider all regions within the noise source volume to be equally probable for a given configuration, and project onto the core geometry as follows:

$$p(v, \mathbf{r}|\mathbf{d}) \propto \frac{1}{\sum_{\mathbf{q}} \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}} \sum_{\mathbf{q}} p(v, \mathbf{x}|\mathbf{d}) \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}. \quad (16)$$

In Equation (16), we divide by a spatial distribution representing the number of configurations that include a core region \mathbf{r} . This choice removes the geometrical bias that arises because inner core regions may be involved in a larger number of configurations. Now, criteria need to be established for the selection of the volume hosting the noise source, the perturbation class, and the source intensity. For

each class, we choose to consider all regions within an asymmetric ellipsoid, satisfying the condition:

$$\frac{(x - x_0)^2}{\sigma_x^2} + \frac{(y - y_0)^2}{\sigma_y^2} + \frac{(z - z_0)^2}{\sigma_z^2} \leq 1. \quad (17)$$

In Equation (17), the center of mass $\mathbf{r}_0 = [x_0, y_0, z_0]$ coincides with the expected position:

$$\mathbf{r}_0 = \frac{1}{\int p(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{r}|\mathbf{d})d\mathbf{r}} \int \mathbf{r}p(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{r}|\mathbf{d})d\mathbf{r}, \quad (18)$$

and the spatial variance in the generic direction k is computed for the two orientations as:

$$\sigma_k^2 = \frac{1}{\int_{\alpha} p(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{r}|\mathbf{d})d\mathbf{r}} \int_{\alpha} |\mathbf{r}_k - \mathbf{r}_{0k}|^2 p(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{r}|\mathbf{d})d\mathbf{r}, \quad (19)$$

where α is the integration domain, either on the left ($\mathbf{r}_k < \mathbf{r}_{0k}$) or on the right ($\mathbf{r}_k > \mathbf{r}_{0k}$) with respect to the center of the ellipsoid. We select the most likely perturbation class such that $\mathbf{v}_{el} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{v}} \int_{V_{el}} p(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{r}|\mathbf{d})d\mathbf{r}$, with V_{el} being the ellipsoid defined by one spatial uncertainty. Finally, we compute the source intensity as the expected value in the solution space.

3.2. Artificial Neural Network Model

In the current study, we use a second model that consists of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) based on a typical feed-forward, fully connected architecture. This model is the result of a preliminary optimization analysis aimed at maximizing output accuracy and improving training stability. The ANN receives as input the amplitude and phase of the elements in the PSD matrix. It provides a multi-task output corresponding to the three inversion tasks, namely the parameters \mathbf{v} , \mathbf{x} and Γ . The hidden block is composed of six hidden layers with a variable number of neurons. The number of neurons increases up to the fifth hidden layer, where it reaches its maximum, and then decreases toward the output layer. Each hidden layer has respectively 540, 630, 720, 810, 990 and 540 neurons. However, starting from the fifth hidden layer, the flow of information is subdivided into three groups of neurons, each specialized for one of the output tasks. The available neurons in each layer are partitioned in a 6:1:1 ratio, corresponding respectively to the localization, classification, and characterization tasks. All neurons in the hidden block are activated using the ReLU function. The output of the neural network is designed to treat the parameters \mathbf{v} , \mathbf{x} and Γ as classification problems. This choice is motivated by the observation that the training process is significantly more stable in terms of number of epochs before the training loss changes trend and begins to increase. Consequently, all output layers are activated using the softmax function, and the neuron corresponding to the maximum value is selected as the solution to the problem. Moreover, the localization output has a six-layer structure, where the layers contain a number of neurons equal to the number of possible surfaces in each dimension of the vector \mathbf{x} . The classification output consists of a single layer with a number of neurons equal to the number of possible perturbation classes. For the characterization task, the continuous range of values for the amplitude of Γ is represented by a set of discrete values. These values represent source intensity levels and constitute the ANN prediction for the characterization of the noise source. The loss function is chosen as the categorical cross-entropy between the predicted and true probability distributions, and it is optimized using the Adam algorithm. The maximum number of epochs was set to 300, with the implementation of an early-stop criterion. This criterion monitors the total loss function at the end of each epoch and checks if the quantity has decreased in the last 20 epochs. If not, the best weights are restored and the training is stopped. For the training of the neural network we generated two datasets. Both include all possible noise source configurations for \mathbf{v} , \mathbf{x} and five source intensity levels. However, one of the two training datasets contains the distorted input data. Specifically, for each noise source configuration and each value of the sensitivity parameter ϵ , ten distinct samples of the distorted matrix $\widehat{\text{PSD}}$ are stored. The prescribed values of ϵ are 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 and do not coincide in the testing.

4. SIGNAL RECONSTRUCTION

The distorted neutron noise measurements discussed in Section 2.2 may be corrected prior to their use within the framework of the Exhaustive Search. Therefore, we investigate a technique that allows reconstructing the clean signals under the assumption that an accurate physical model is available. This technique relies on the existence of a set of parameters \mathbf{q}_0 such that the residual between the clean measurements \mathbf{d} and the corresponding model predictions vanishes for each detector response:

$$\exists \mathbf{q}_0 \text{ such that } \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{d} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_0)\Gamma_0 = 0, \quad (20)$$

where Γ_0 represents the actual periodic functions of the perturbations. The total residual between measurements and model predictions consists of two contributions: the first, \mathbf{r}_m , arises from the multiplicative distortion, while the second, \mathbf{r}_q , stems from the difference between the estimated parameters and the ones associated with the true inverse solution. Using the assumption (20) and the relationship $\Gamma(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{A}^+(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_0)\Gamma_0$, partial and total residuals can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{r}_m(\mathbf{q}_0) = \tilde{\mathbf{d}} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_0)\Gamma_0, \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_q(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q}_0) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_0)\Gamma_0 - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{A}^+(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_0)\Gamma_0, \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_t(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q}_0) = \mathbf{r}_m + \mathbf{r}_q = \tilde{\mathbf{d}} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{A}^+(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_0)\Gamma_0. \quad (23)$$

Minimizing the total residual \mathbf{r}_t with respect to \mathbf{q} does not necessarily yield the correct solution, whereas this condition is ensured by the expression for \mathbf{r}_q . Consequently, the measurements are corrected by a set of distortion factors η , thus exploiting the information of multiplicative distortion associated with each detector response, and by assuming that the residual \mathbf{r}_m is entirely explained by these factors:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{d}} = \eta \circ \mathbf{d} \implies \eta(\mathbf{q}) = \tilde{\mathbf{d}} \oslash [\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})\Gamma_0]. \quad (24)$$

In Equation (24), the operator \oslash denotes element-wise division. We note that, for a given configuration \mathbf{q}_0 , there exists an infinite number of pairs (Γ_0, η) that can reproduce the distortion. Therefore, an additional condition must be introduced to uniquely determine the vector η . A practical way to resolve this indeterminacy is to impose the constraint $\sum_d \varepsilon_d^2 = N_d \tilde{\varepsilon}^2$, where $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ is the expected root mean square value, estimated from the discrepancies between the measurements and the least-squares predictions. This condition not only introduces a degree of uncertainty in estimating the actual periodic functions of the perturbations, but also leads to a second-order equation for the estimated $\tilde{\Gamma}(\mathbf{q}_0)$. Although physical constraints can be used to select a meaningful root, we have observed that both solutions of this equation may satisfy the physical conditions. In such cases, we select the largest value of $\tilde{\Gamma}(\mathbf{q}_0)$. Nevertheless, we have verified that this choice does not affect the final solution of the nonlinear inverse problem, provided that the distortion factors and $\tilde{\Gamma}(\mathbf{q}_0)$ are consistently determined through Equation (24). Under this condition, the residuals to be minimized are expressed as:

$$\mathbf{r}_q(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{q}_0) = \mathbf{d} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})\Gamma(\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{r}_t - \mathbf{r}_m = [\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{A}^+(\mathbf{q})] \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_0)\tilde{\Gamma}(\mathbf{q}_0), \quad (25)$$

which become zero only if $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q}_0$, with \mathbf{q}_0 being the unique solution of the non-linear inverse problem in the search space. The ES algorithm described in Section 3.1 requires only minor adjustments and avoids computing the residuals for all combinations of \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{q}_0 , which would entail a substantial additional computational cost. Instead, while exploring the search space it is sufficient to include a preliminary step to reconstruct the clean signal using Equation (24), and then employ this corrected dataset to evaluate the discrepancy functional defined in Equation (12).

5. SENSITIVITY TO MEASUREMENT QUALITY

To test the ES and the ANN-based frameworks, we use the research reactor CROCUS, located at EPFL and described in [4]. This reactor has been modeled for simulations of neutron noise experiments within

the CORTEX project [5]. We use the neutron noise solver CORE SIM+ [6], which is based on traditional linear noise theory and the two-group diffusion approximation in the frequency domain. In the current application, we use synthetic detector signals, and actual measurements will be analyzed in future work. We consider a reactor configuration with 9 thermal neutron detectors positioned in the core and the reflector. For the inverse problem, the localization task on the core radial plane consists of selecting two indices among 20 possible surfaces perpendicular to the x -axis, and two indices among 20 possible surfaces perpendicular to the y -axis, resulting in 43790 possible noise source volumes. The classification search space, instead, contains three possible source shape functions: a uniform fuel pin vibration in the x direction, a uniform fuel pin vibration in the y direction, and a coolant density fluctuation. Only scenarios with one single noise source are considered. A sensitivity analysis is carried out with respect to the parameter ε , considering the values 0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.06, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6. For each value, 1000 tests are generated, each comprising a set of nine distorted signals associated with the nine detectors. The distortion factors are sampled as discussed in Section 2.2. The clean signals are generated by uniformly sampling a localization vector \mathbf{x} , a class \mathbf{v} , and a noise source intensity $|\Gamma|$ within the interval $[0, 1]$. Each test consists of solving an inverse problem, and predictions from the methodologies are used to assess their expected accuracies. Consequently, the distorted matrix $\widetilde{\text{PSD}}$ is stored for each test. For the three tasks, we define the following accuracy metrics:

$$\eta_v = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_j^{N_t} \delta(\mathbf{v}_j = \mathbf{v}_j^{\text{ref}}), \quad \eta_x = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_j^{N_t} \eta_{x1,j} \eta_{x2,j}, \quad \eta_\Gamma = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_j^{N_t} \left(1 - \frac{|\gamma_j - \gamma_j^{\text{ref}}|}{N_\gamma - 1} \right), \quad (26)$$

where N_t is the number of tests, “ref” denotes the true solution, and γ represents the source intensity level, corresponding to the index of the mesh used for the ANN model to discretize the range $[0, 1]$ into N_γ values. The localization accuracy η_x is the product of two factors: the first represents the intersection between the predicted and reference volumes, while the second is a penalization factor accounting for incorrectly predicted regions. These factors are defined as follows:

$$\eta_{x1} = \frac{N^{gss}}{N^{gss} + N^{mss}}, \quad \eta_{x2} = \exp \left(-a \frac{N^{wrg}}{N^{\text{tot}} - N^{gss} - N^{mss}} \right), \quad (27)$$

where N denotes the number of regions, and the superscripts “gss”, “mss”, “wrg”, and “tot” stand for guessed, missed, wrong, and total, respectively. The coefficient a is chosen equal to $-\ln(0.01)$, so that when the number of wrongly predicted regions reaches its maximum while $\eta_{x1} = 1$, the resulting localization accuracy equals 0.01. Figure 1 shows the accuracies of the presented techniques as a function of the sensitivity parameter ε . The labels “GMin” and “Bayesian” indicate ES solutions obtained using the two strategies for determining the problem solution, while “ANN(clean)” and “ANN(distorted)” correspond to the solutions provided by the neural network trained on datasets with clean and distorted signals, respectively. Finally, “+reconstruct” identifies the case in which the ES algorithm processes the clean signals as reconstructed via the technique discussed in Section 4.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The Exhaustive Search always provides the exact solution when synthetic clean detector signals are used, demonstrating that the inverse problem admits a unique solution. Its accuracy rapidly decreases as the measurement distortion increases, as expected from the ill-posed nature of inverse problems. Combining the ES algorithm with a Bayesian approach to determine the noise source volume improves the final solution by roughly 20% in the localization and characterization tasks compared to the global minimum criterion, while maintaining a similar classification accuracy. The ANN model trained with clean signals, is less accurate than ES for small distortions, but it is less sensitive as the distortion increases. This robustness is evident when the neural network is trained and tested with consistent distorted signals. This is demonstrated by the accuracies for the three tasks, which remain nearly constant for any distortion level. A possible explanation of this behavior is that the ANN model recognizes

Figure 1. Accuracies of the techniques as a function of the sensitivity parameter ε .

a common pattern in the dataset, namely the presence of a multiplicative Gaussian distortion in the signals, although confirmation of this aspect requires a deeper analysis. Another open question is whether different types of multiplicative distortion could still be accurately interpreted if the training were performed only with Gaussian noise. Finally, the study shows that ES combined with the signal reconstruction technique achieves the best accuracy and robustness. Considering that the detector signals are expected to represent the same underlying phenomenon, the reconstruction enforces consistency among them via the physical model. This approach successfully predicts the class and localization of the noise source in all cases, showing that the nonlinear relationship between the solution and the detector signals is well reproduced. On the other hand, the characterization accuracy gradually decreases with increasing distortion. This can be explained by the fact that the reconstruction and the generation of the clean signal are based on the same physical model. We report the computational cost of the techniques “ANN(distorted)” and “ES+reconstruct” in terms of runtime on a single laptop processor. Generating the dataset of distorted signals took about one minute, ANN training required roughly one day, and execution took one second. In contrast, ES requires up to 30 seconds to provide a solution.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge SSM for funding, and EPFL for providing the homogenized cross sections.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Galia, P. Vinai, and C. Demazière. “Adjoint-based exhaustive search for neutron noise sources of arbitrary size.” *(to be submitted)*.
- [2] I. Pázsit and C. Demazière. “Noise techniques in nuclear systems.” In *Handbook of Nuclear Engineering*, pp. 1629–1737. Springer (2010).
- [3] I. Pázsit. “Control-rod models and vibration induced noise.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 15**(7), pp. 333–346 (1988).
- [4] “A benchmark on the calculation of kinetic parameters based on reactivity effect experiments in the CROCUS reactor.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 33**(8), pp. 739–748 (2006).
- [5] C. Demazière, P. Vinai, M. Hursin, S. Kollias, J. Herb, et al. “Overview of the CORTEX project.” *Proceedings of PHYSOR 2018*, pp. 2971–2980 (2018).
- [6] A. Mylonakis, P. Vinai, and C. Demazière. “CORE SIM+: A flexible diffusion-based solver for neutron noise simulations.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 155**, p. 108149 (2021).